
On-the-fly rapid immunoassay for neonatal sepsis diagnosis: C-reactive protein accurate determination using magnetic graphene-based micromotors.

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Abstract

Based on the exceptional and new opened biosensing possibilities of self-propelled micromotors, a micromotor-based immunoassay (MIm) has smartly been designed for C-reactive protein (CRP) determination in plasma of preterm infants with sepsis suspicion.

The design of the micromotors involved the electrosynthesis of a carbon-based outer layer (for antibody functionalization), an intermediate Ni layer (for magnetic guidance and stopped flow operations) and PtNPs inner catalytic layer (for catalytic bubble propulsion).

Micromotors biofunctionalization on the outer layer (using carbon black (CB), reduced graphene oxide (rGO) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), and biocompatible propulsion capabilities, were carefully studied. Magnetic rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors exhibited the most efficient and reproducible (CV = 9%) anti-CRP functionalization, controlled stopped-flow operations as well as efficient bubble propulsion (1% H₂O₂, 1.5% NaCh, speed 140 μm s⁻¹). Analytical performance of MIm was excellent, allowing the direct (without dilution), sensitive (LOD = 0.80 μg/mL), and accurate CRP determination (E_r = 1%) in hardly available preterm babies' plasma samples with suspected sepsis using very low volumes (< 10 μL) and in just 5 min of *on-the-fly* bioassay.

Overall, the results obtained allowed the fast and reliable sepsis diagnostics in preterm babies' individuals with suspected sepsis, not only proving the usefulness of the approach as its potential utilization as *point-of-care* device for clinical analysis but drawing new horizons in extremely low sample volumes-based diagnostics.

1. Introduction

Micro and nanomotors that convert chemical energy or an external stimulus (magnetic, ultrasound or light) into autonomous propulsion have gained a great and continuous growing attention in the last decade (Zha *et al.*, 2018; Karshalev *et al.*, 2018). Among other fields, clinical diagnostic and biosensing capabilities of these micro/nano synthetic machines have opened a plethora of new bioanalytical applications. Some of the most important challenges in biomedical applications are the low detection limits required for early disease detection and the ultra-small sample volumes commonly available. In these situations, sensitivity is usually limited by the inefficient transport of the analyte towards the bioreceptor for their interaction, due to the quiescent conditions ordinarily used in such assays or the ineffective convection transport in so low volume samples. In this sense, the self-propelled and autonomous propulsion of bioreceptor-modified micromotors around a complex sample, to find and bound the analyte, represents a new paradigm in analytical chemistry (Wang, 2016; Kong *et al.*, 2018). In particular, bubble-propelled catalytic micro/nano motors are especially appropriate due to their rapid propulsion and the mixing associated effect by the generated microbubbles tail. This fluid mixing effect leads to a favorable hydrodynamic environment, which enhances the kinetics of the binding reaction and promotes the interaction of the target analytes with the receptor (Wang, 2016; Orozco *et al.*, 2014; Morales-Narváez *et al.*, 2014; Campuzano *et al.*, 2011a; Kagan *et al.*, 2011). This process is especially efficient in ultraminiaturized samples with minimal sample preparations.

Different biological receptors such as nucleic acids (Kagan *et al.*, 2011), aptamers (Esteban-Fernández de Ávila *et al.*, 2016; Molinero-Fernández *et al.*, 2017; Molinero-Fernández *et al.*, 2018), and lectins (Campuzano *et al.*, 2011b; Maria-Hormigos *et al.*, 2017) have been immobilized on the surface of micromotors to perform new *on-the-fly* detection schemes with higher efficiency and shorter times. Specially, antibodies-modified micromotors have demonstrated their ability to detect different targets molecules (García *et al.*, 2013; Vilela *et al.*, 2014) such as tumoral cells (Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2011),

cancer biomarkers (Yu *et al.*, 2014), spores of *Bacillus anthracis* (Orozco *et al.*, 2015) and cortisol (Esteban-Fernández de Ávila *et al.*, 2017).

The material used for the construction of the outer micromotor layer is crucial, since it affects its capacity of binding biomolecules on its surface as well as micromotors' propulsion efficiency. Different nanomaterials and strategies have been previously explored for the construction of the outer layer supporting the biomolecules such as gold sputtering that produces only a partial modification of the half outer micromotors layer, affecting their overall capacity of biomolecule immobilization and mobility (Esteban-Fernández de Ávila *et al.*, 2017); gold nanoparticles decoration that implies additional and more complex stages (Yu *et al.*, 2014); or electro-copolymerization (García *et al.*, 2013), which need rigorous control of monomers concentration and doping in order to maintain the morphology and performance of the micromotors.

On the other hand, carbon nanomaterials possess unique physical and chemical properties that allow both, biomolecules immobilization in the micromotor outer layer (Maria-Hormigos *et al.*, 2018) as well as high micromotor speeds when suitable catalysts are also used in the inner layer (Martín *et al.*, 2015; Maria-Hormigos *et al.*, 2016).

On the other hand, C-reactive protein (CRP) is a homopentameric plasmatic protein with a molecular weight of 118 kDa that is produced mainly in liver and lung as response to inflammation (Vashist *et al.*, 2016). CRP is a widely studied protein due to its high interest as early indicator of infectious or inflammatory conditions, related to various diseases, disorders and pathological conditions (Agrawal *et al.*, 2014; Brito *et al.*, 2015; Clyne y Olshaker, 1999). An elevation in its plasmatic levels can be directly related to the severity of the disease, increasing up to 1000-fold during an acute inflammation phase (Hisamuddin *et al.*, 2015; Yuan *et al.*, 2013; Boonkasidecha *et al.*, 2013). Elevated CRP levels have been directly related to the risk of suffering cardiovascular disease, where blood serum concentration ranges < 1 , $1-3$ and > 3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ correlates with low, moderate and high risk, respectively. Especially important is the role of CRP in the diagnosis of sepsis. Early and accurate diagnosis is crucial to decrease mortality and to avoid unnecessary exposure to antibiotics, in order to reduce

antibiotic resistance and severe side effects in patients. In this sense, CRP has demonstrated to be a late biomarker of neonatal infections and a good marker of the response to antibiotic therapy (Simon *et al.*, 2004; Vashist *et al.*, 2016). Values higher than 10 µg/mL in blood, can be considered positive for sepsis.

However, sepsis diagnosis is still a challenge and complex phenomenon due to the unspecific signs and symptoms and the absence of an ideal biomarker. Besides, the need to carry out serial analysis to improve diagnosis and disease monitoring, constitutes an additional problem, especially for those patients where low volume samples are available such as neonates. Hence, the development of reliable, cost-effective, sensitive, and fast approaches for CRP detection and monitoring, which in turn allow the use of low sample volumes, is particularly important in clinical analysis.

CRP determination has been carried out by different techniques such as chemiluminescence and fluorescence immunoassays, or enzyme linked immunosorbent and immunoturbidimetric assays. They are sensitive, but usually suffer from important sample and reagent consumption. Moreover, routinely, they are performed in central laboratories and results are delayed, which is highly incompatible with the need to make quick decisions. In that sense, new approaches to surpass those limitations have been developed during the last years (Vashist *et al.*, 2016). Among them, electrochemical immunosensors are one of the most attractive techniques for the detection of clinical samples by virtue of their low cost, high sensitivity, rapidity, and portability. (Yáñez-Sedeño *et al.*, 2017). Several electrochemical immunosensors for CRP have been developed (Vermeeren *et al.*, 2011; Esteban-Fernández de Ávila *et al.*, 2013; Kumar and Prasad, 2012; Ibupoto *et al.*, 2012; Bryan *et al.*, 2012; Fakanya and Tohill, 2014; Yagati *et al.*, 2016; Liu *et al.*, 2016; Thangamuthu *et al.*, 2018; Kowalczyk *et al.*, 2018; Boonkaew *et al.*, 2019; Molinero-Fernández *et al.*, 2019). However, to the best of our knowledge, the micromotors technology has not been explored for CRP determination.

Because of the use of micromotors as new tools in immunoassays provides a new paradigm, as stated above, our hypothesis is that antibody-functionalized micromotors can swim autonomously around the sample to bind actively the

specific analyte, without the need of external stirring. The expected efficient movement of the micromotors and the generated microbubbles tails, can enhance the fluid mixing, and consequently improving the efficiency of the biorecognition event. This principle can favor a fast strategy for CRP determination in extremely small volume samples, such as those obtained from preterm babies with sepsis suspicion.

In this work, we have proposed the first micromotor-based immunoassay (MIm) for the *on-the-fly* CRP determination. In the following sections, we will demonstrate the analytical potency of this biosensing approach for CRP rapid and accurate determination in clinical samples such as preterm infants' plasma.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagent and solutions

CRP (8C72) and two paired monoclonal mouse anti-human CRP antibodies (4C28C HRP-conjugated and 4C28B biotinylated) were obtained from HyTest (Turku, Finland).

Dilution of CRP and anti-human CRP antibodies were prepared in PBS 0.1M phosphate (Scharlau, 99%), 0.138M NaCl (Scharlau, 99%) and 2.7 mM KCl (Scharlau, 99%) buffer solution pH 7.5.

Enzyme substrate PERDROGEN™ 30% H₂O₂, Hydroquinone, Bovine serum albumin (BSA), Streptavidin, 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide (EDC), N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide (NHS) and Sodium Cholate (NaCh) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). Hydroquinone and peroxide solutions were prepared in phosphate buffer 0.1 M, pH 7 (PB). EDC, NHS and Streptavidin solutions were prepared in MES buffer 0.1 M pH 5.0. MES monohydrate was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

For the micromotors synthesis, the 5 µm-diameter conical pores polycarbonate membranes (PC) were purchase from Whatman (Maidstone, UK). Multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs), Carbon Black (CB, < 50 nm particle size), Graphene Oxide (GO, 2 mg/mL dispersion in water) and Chloroplatinic acid

hydrate were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain) and used without further purification.

2.2. Samples

European Reference Material ERM-DA474/IFCC with a CRP concentration of 41.2 ± 2.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain).

Hospital Clínico San Carlos (Madrid, Spain) provided unique plasma samples from preterm neonates, with sepsis suspicion. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital and parental informed consent was obtained before the collection of blood samples. The babies were included in the study since blood sampling was needed as part of the standard care in the intensive care unit and not for the only purpose of the present study.

2.3. Apparatus and electrodes

Amperometric measurements were carried out with a multi potentiostat/galvanostat, μSTAT 8000 from DropSens, (Oviedo, Spain), which incorporates the software "DropView 8400". Screen-printed carbon electrodes DRP-110 (4 mm \varnothing) (Dropsens) including a silver pseudoreference electrode and a carbon counter electrode, were used. Advanced Vortex Mixer-ZX3 from Velp Scientifica and Pulsing Vortex Mixer from VWR Signature were used for incubation stages. Magnetic block DynaMag™-2 were obtained from ThermoFisher and used for handling of magnetic micromotors, and Magnetic racks (Dropsens) to control the attraction of magnetic micromotors to the SPCE were also used.

Inverted optical microscope (Nikon Eclipse Instrument Inc. Ti-S/L100), Zyla sCMOS camera and NIS element software were used for capturing images and tracking the speed of micromotors. An Epifluorescence attachment with a G-2A filter cube were used for fluorescence measures. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained with a JEOL JSM 6335F instrument, using an acceleration voltage of 22 kV. Raman spectrums were obtained with a WiTec Alpha 300AR Confocal Raman Microscope, using 1 mW laser power (laser wavelength: 532 nm).

2.4. Micromotor synthesis

The carbon nanomaterials deposition was prepared by electrochemical reduction (rGO, MWCNTs) or direct deposition (CB) into 5 μm diameter conical pores of a polycarbonate membrane (Maria-Hormigos *et al.*, 2016). The S4 branched side of the membrane was treated with a sputtered thin gold film to perform as a working electrode. The membrane was assembled in a Teflon plating cell with aluminum foil serving as an electrical contact to the working electrode for the subsequent electrodeposition. Graphene oxide (rGO) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (0.1 mg/mL) were first dispersed in a solution containing 0.1 M H_2SO_4 and 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min. CB was dispersed in a solution containing 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 by ultrasonication for 15 min. The electrochemical deposition of rGO and MWCNTs was carried out using cyclic voltammetry (CV, over +0.3 to -1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl), at 50 mV s^{-1} , for ten cycles; $n = 10$), using a Pt wire as counter electrode. For CB direct deposition, the CB dispersion was dipped into the Teflon cell and allowed to stand for 30 min to promote CB film formation in the pores of the membrane template. Also, a magnetic layer of Ni was incorporated in the micromotor structure for efficient magnetic control of the micromotor. The nickel tube layer was plated inside the reduced carbon layer by galvanostatic method. First, 10 pulses of -20 mA were applied for 0.1s to generate nucleation spots. Then, a constant current of -6 mA was applied for 300 s to grow the nickel layer. Subsequently, a platinum layer was plated inside the carbon nanomaterial and nickel layers. The inner PtNPs layer was deposited by amperometry at -0.4 V for 750 s from an aqueous solution containing 4 mM of H_2PtCl_6 in 0.5 M acid boric. The sputtered gold layer was gently hand polished with 1 μm alumina slurry. After that, the membrane was dissolved in methylene chloride for 30 min to completely release the microtubes. The micromotors were placed on the magnet holding block and the supernatant was removed. Afterward, successive washes with isopropanol and ethanol (both twice) and ultrapure water (18.2 $\text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$, three times) were performed respectively, with a 2 min on the magnet holding block between each wash. All microtubes were stored in ultrapure water (800 μL) at room temperature when are not in use. The template preparation method resulted in decidedly reproducible micromotors.

For control experiments, rGO/MWCNTs/CB/Ni micromotors were synthesized following the same fabrication protocol but without the electrodeposition of platinum.

2.5. Micromotors functionalization

1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide (EDC) / N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide (NHS) chemistry was used to activate the carboxyl terminated groups from the carbon materials layer for conjugation with streptavidin. For this purpose, a stock solution of 800 μL (160000 microengines approximately) for each different batch of micromotors, containing rGO, MWCNTs or CB in the outer layer, were treated with 200 μL of a 100 mM EDC/NHS solution prepared in 0.1 M MES buffer, pH 5.0 for 30 min at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. After two washing steps with MES buffer, the activated micromotors were incubated with 200 μL of a 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptavidin solution in 0.1 M MES buffer, pH 5.0, for 1 h at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Two washing steps with MES buffer and an additional washing step with PBS were carried out to eliminate the excess of streptavidin.

Then, streptavidin modified micromotors were incubated in a solution containing 1000 μL of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ biotinylated anti-CRP antibody (capture antibody). After room temperature incubation under stirring for 30 min, the tube was placed on the magnetic holding block and the supernatant was removed. Immediately, it was followed by twice washing steps with 1000 μL of PBS buffer and the micromotors were resuspended in 800 μL of PBS and maintained at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

For outer layer binding capacity assessment, biotin-fluorophore labeled reagent (Atto 550-biotin) was used. In this sense, three batches containing 8 μL of different carbon outer layer micromotors each, and after streptavidin immobilization (under excess conditions), were incubated in a 5% BSA blocking solution during 45 min, followed by three washing steps with 100 μL of PBS. Then, each micromotors batch was incubated with 10 μL of biotin-fluorophore labeled reagent in PBS (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) during 15 min. Finally, adequate washing steps were carried out prior to their fluorimetric detection.

2.6. Development of CRP-micromotor immunoassay

In detail, 10 μL of micromotors suspension (2000 micromotors approx.) modified with the capture antibody were deposited into a test tube. Then, the sample and detection antibody were added (10 μL total volume, of which 7 μL were sample) to perform the sandwich immunocomplex in one step. In order to provide the micromotors' propulsion, the surfactant NaCh (1.5%) and H_2O_2 (1%), which allows the catalytic reaction responsible of the bubble formation in the inner layer of the micromotor, were also deposited into the tube. The biological interaction was boosted thanks to the autonomous movement of the modified micromotors in so small volume. After 5 min, the micromotors propulsion was stopped by addition of 200 μL of PBS. Thanks to their magnetic characteristics (intermediate magnetic layer of nickel), micromotors were retained and the supernatant was removed, followed by three washing steps.

2.7. Electrochemical measurements

Once the immunoaffinity interactions were complete the micromotors-immunocomplexes were re-suspended in 45 μL of hydroquinone solution (1 mM) and magnetically captured on the working electrodes of the SPCE. Amperometric measurements were performed at -0.20 V after addition of 5 μL of hydrogen peroxide solution (5 mM final concentration). The signals were calculated as the difference between the steady-state and the background currents after 100 s.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Micromotor-based immunoassay strategy

Tubular micromotors constituted by rGO as functionalization support outer layer covered with streptavidin, an intermediate magnetic Ni and internal PtNPs catalytic layer were electrosynthesized for the *on-the-fly* immunoassay strategy. The micromotor immunoassay design is depicted in **Figure IV.1.1**. Streptavidin rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors were previously functionalized with anti-CRP capture antibody. These functionalized micromotors were left in a solution that contained the protein target (CRP), anti-CRP detection antibody labeled with HRP and the fuel solution. Catalytic micromotor propulsion was carried out under optimized

surfactant NaCh (1.5%) and fuel H₂O₂ (1%) conditions due to the ejection of oxygen bubbles from H₂O₂ decomposition in the PtNPs inner micromotor layer. The biological interactions were boosted thanks to the autonomous propulsion of the functionalized micromotors in low volumes benefiting the immunocomplex formation. Thanks to their magnetic micromotor properties, the assay was flow-stopped (just in 5 min), the micromotors washed, the supernatant removed, and electrochemical detection was carried out on SPCE at -0.20 V (5 mM H₂O₂, 1 mM Hydroquinone (HQ)).

Figure IV.1.1. Magnetic micromotor-based immunoassay for CRP determination.

3.2. Outer carbon layer composition selection: study of micromotors immunocomplex formation capabilities

In this work, micromotors outer layer based on carbon nanomaterials with different dimensionality have been electrosynthesized: carbon black (CB, 3D), reduced graphene oxide (rGO, 2D) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs, 1D).

The streptavidin immobilization capacity of the different carbon nanomaterials was evaluated by the formation of the whole biotinylated-immunocomplex-HRP with electrochemical detection, as well as corroborated by the use of a fluorophore-labeled biotin.

As observed in **Figure IV.1.2A** (bars in blue), higher amperometric signal was observed for rGO micromotors in comparison with MWCNTs and CB micromotors, through control experiments performing the whole electrochemical immunoassay using the three carbon-based micromotors under mechanical stirring, and without the contribution of the propulsion efficiency (without PtNPs catalytic layer). Besides, **Figure IV.1.2A** (white bars), also shows how rGO micromotors present a higher fluorescence signal in comparison with MWCNTs and CB micromotors. Consequently, the results obtained by both electrochemical and fluorescence approaches indicated higher streptavidin immobilization capacity, and subsequently higher capture antibody binding on rGO micromotors in comparison with MWCNTs and especially with CB-based micromotors, where lower density of carboxylic groups was expected.

Figure IV.1.2. Influence of the carbon nanomaterial outer layer on the capabilities of the micromotors immunoassay: (A) Immobilization capacity assay: fluorescence signals due to the Atto-550-biotin bound to the streptavidin-micromotors (left axis, bars in white); and amperometric signals with immunocomplex formation under stirring conditions (5 min, 1.5% NaCh, 1% H₂O₂, in absence of inner PtNPs catalytic layer) (right axis, bars in blue). (B) Speed of the different carbon nanomaterials micromotors in PBS: Unfunctionalized, bars in blue; functionalized with streptavidin and capture antibody, bars in white (1.5% NaCh, 1% H₂O₂, 5 min). (C) Amperometric signals for the *on-the-fly* immunoassay (1.5% NaCh, 1% H₂O₂, 5 min).

The micromotor speeds of the functionalized micromotors with the specific antibody, and under optimized propulsion conditions (1% H₂O₂, 1.5% NaCh; see optimization in **section 3.3**) were quite similar for both outer layers micromotors composed by rGO or MWCNTs, while appreciable smaller ones for CB layer. This fact could be explained because of the highest surface roughness of CB-based

micromotors leads to a large friction force, resulting in a reduced speed in comparison with smoother ones such as rGO and MWCNTs-based micromotors (Maria-Hormigos *et al.*, 2016). Besides and in all cases, carbon functionalized micromotor speeds decreased ($\approx 25\%$) in comparison with those obtained when unfunctionalized carbon-based micromotors were used, because of the loaded anti-CRP antibody on board. (**Figure IV.1.2B**).

Figure IV.1.2C shows the overall performance of the self-propelled immunoassay under optimized propulsion conditions (1% H₂O₂, 1.5% NaCh; see optimization in **section 3.3**), combining carbon-based micromotors functionalization and speed capabilities. Following the previous reasoning, CB micromotors presented the lower amperometric signals, due to the lower propulsion efficiency and binding capacity.

The differences observed in binding capabilities among the carbon-based micromotors, were in agreement with the Raman spectra (**Figure IV.1.3**). Indeed, carbon allotropes showed their fingerprints mostly by D and G band at 1347 cm⁻¹ and 1601 cm⁻¹, respectively. The D band arises from the out-of-plane vibrational modes and is indicative of the number of sp³ carbon atoms present, whereas the G band arises from the presence of in-plane sp² vibrations. It is well known that the EDC/NHS chemistry for biomolecules immobilization on carbon is based and highly dependent on sp³ chemistry. These facts support our reasoning based on correlate the sp³ defect level of the three carbon nanomaterials studied with the extension of streptavidin immobilization that has experimentally been observed. The ratio between the intensity of the D band and the G band (I_D/I_G) is also typically used as indicative of the number of defects in the carbon allotropes. The higher I_D/I_G ratio observed in the rGO, indicates a higher number of defects (carboxylic, epoxy, etc. groups), which can be related with its higher streptavidin immobilization.

Figure IV.1.3. Raman spectra corresponding to the outer layer of the carbon-based micromotors.

Although as it was discussed above, rGO and MWCNTs micromotors showed the best analytical performance in terms of biofunctionalization and speed capabilities; reproducibility was clearly improved when rGO was used (CV = 9% vs 12% for rGO and MWCNTs), and hence these micromotors (rGO/Ni/PtNPs) were chosen for the next experiments. **Figure IV.1.4** shows the morphology and elemental composition of these selected rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors towards SEM and EDX images, respectively. The conical micromotor shape with dimensions of 5 μm of width and 10 μm of length, as well as the presence of C, Ni, and Pt from outer, intermediate and inner layers, demonstrated the success of the micromotor electrosynthesis. These results were also confirmed for the other carbon-based micromotors, results are not shown.

Figure IV.1.4. SEM images and EDX analysis of the rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors. Scale bar: 5 μ m.

3.3. Optimization of the rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotor-based immunoassay

The number of rGO micromotors, the immunoassay performance (antibody concentrations, non-specific adsorption, incubation times), and propulsion conditions have been deeply studied. **Table IV.1.1** lists the relevant parameters optimized for this unique *on-the-fly* immunoassay is well-separated blocks.

Table IV.1.1. Optimization of the micromotor-based immunoassay.

Parameter	Tested Range	Selected Value
Micromotors number	200 - 2400	2000
[Capture Ab] μ g/mL	0 - 12	10
Capture Ab incubation time, min	0 - 60	30
[Detection Ab] μ g/mL	0 - 12.5	10
Block step, [BSA] %	0 - 7.5	2.5
Block step incubation time, min	0 - 60	30
Fuel, [H ₂ O ₂] %	0.5 - 5	1
Protein + Detection Ab incubation time, min	0 - 15	5

The influence of the number of micromotors was evaluated in the range between 200 and 2400 micromotors in the presence of an excess of CRP and

anti-CRP antibody (5 min, 10 μ L, 1% H_2O_2 , 1.5% NaCh) showing an increase in the cathodic current with the micromotors loading up to 2000 micromotors followed by a plateau. Consequently, 2000 micromotors were chosen as the optimum value.

The amount of both, capture antibody immobilized onto the micromotors surface, and detection antibody labeled with HRP was evaluated. The maximum current intensities were obtained at 10 μ g/mL for both antibodies, followed by a plateau as indicative of saturation of binding sites. In order to diminish non-specific adsorption, a blocking step with BSA was tackled after capture antibody immobilization, noticing that 30 min and 2.5% BSA reduce the unspecific response to a negligible current (< 1%).

In contrast with conventional immunosensors, where the analyte interacts with the usually immobilized specific antibody by diffusion or external stirring of the solution, in the reported immunoassay approach, self-propelled micromotors actively move around the sample to bind the analyte. In this sense, micromotors propulsion (fuel and surfactant concentrations), as well as the required time for the recognition stage, were also carefully studied.

Autonomous propulsion of micromotors is produced through the chemical reaction of hydrogen peroxide as fuel reactant in their PtNPs inner layer ejecting oxygen bubbles. H_2O_2 concentration is a key parameter, since larger amount implies fast movement of micromotors but restricts the recognition event, producing an excess of bubbles in the solution, and the inactivation of the enzyme by substrate excess. However, a low fuel concentration reduces the speed of micromotors, slowing down the probability of collisions with the target protein, and avoiding sample homogenization. As depicted in **Figure IV.1.5A**, 1 % (v/v) H_2O_2 produces the best MIm performance in comparison not only with the static and mechanical stirring controls, but with those obtained for other lower and higher fuel concentrations. Indeed, it is worthy to remark that mechanical stirring in so small volume samples produced lower signal than the self-propelled motion. These results reflect the high efficiency of the micromotors propulsion and corresponding localized fluid convection in samples of small volumes (< 10 μ L).

Related to the time that micromotors move around the sample, as time increases, greater the possibility of biorecognition event and hence the signal. However, an excess of time also produces some of the effects mentioned above for larger amount of the fuel. In this sense, **Figure IV.1.5B** shows just 5 min as the best time to obtain the maximum current.

Figure IV.1.5. MIm propulsion performance: (A) static and mechanical stirring controls as well as fuel concentration dependence (for 5 min. incubation); (B) incubation time dependence (at 1% H₂O₂, 1.5% NaCh).

Besides, the presence of surfactant in the media is essential for the adequate micromotors propulsion with a minimum H₂O₂ concentration, and hence the use of surfactant also helps to avoid the unwanted effects derived from the use of H₂O₂ as fuel, especially when the HRP enzyme is used for the enzymatic transduction stated above.

However, the use of surfactants at elevated concentrations can also affect negatively the immunoassay performance, since they can denature proteins, break interactions protein-protein and desorb biomolecules from solid phases among others (Selby, 1999; Otzen, 2011). **Figure IV.1.6A** represents the immunoassay signal variation for different H₂O₂ concentrations with and without surfactant addition at the most common concentration used in the literature (1.5% (v/v) of NaCh). (Wang et al., 2014). As can be observed, at 1% H₂O₂, the presence of 1.5% (v/v) of NaCh improves clearly the MIm signal. Nevertheless, at higher peroxide concentrations (3%), the MIm signal is comparable to that obtained in presence of surfactant but lower H₂O₂ concentration. These findings

also meet the micromotor speeds observed. Indeed, the micromotor speeds under surfactant conditions ($130 \pm 40 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$) were comparable with those obtained under higher fuel conditions but without NaCh ($120 \pm 40 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$).

It is also interesting to remark the effect of the surfactant on the affinity reaction time (*on-the-fly* capture) (**Figure IV.1.6B**). At times less than 5 min, the presence of surfactant increased the MIm signal, due to the improved movement of the micromotors. However, when incubation time is increased over those times, the MIm signal diminished. It is hypothesized that this effect is due to the largely exposition time of the molecular interferences of the surfactant in antibody-antigen interactions. Hence, a compromise between the fuel concentrations and the analysis times should be reached. The addition of surfactant (1.5%) allows to decrease the H_2O_2 concentration at 1% and yielded an assay time of just 5 min. These key-conditions allowed a controlled micromotor propulsion without losing of immunoassay performance (see **Table IV.1.1**).

Figure IV.1.6. Effect of the H_2O_2 concentration and time in the immunocomplex formation in absence and presence of surfactant (1.5% of NaCh) in the MIm response: (A) Dependence of the H_2O_2 concentration (5 minutes *on-the-fly* capture). (B) Dependence of the *on-the-fly* capture time: 1.5% NaCh; 1% H_2O_2 in red; only 3% H_2O_2 in black.

3.4. Analytical performance of micromotor-based immunoassay and neonate sample analysis

The analytical characteristics of the MIm were deeply studied. Linear CRP calibration plot (2–100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, $r = 0.992$) was obtained (**Figure IV.1.7**). LOD and LOQ of 0.8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 2.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were estimated accordingly to the $S/N = 3$ and

S/N = 10 criteria, respectively (S was estimated as SD (n =10) obtained during the measurement of the current intensity from the lowest CRP concentration used in the calibration, 2.0 µg/mL).

Precision was evaluated at two CRP concentrations (2 and 10 µg/mL). The intra-assays precision reached a value of CV = 8.0% (n = 5) for both concentrations, while the inter-assays precision gave CV values of 12% and 15% (n = 5 days), for 2 and 10 µg/mL concentrations, respectively.

Figure IV.1.7. Calibration plot of the MIm (1.5% NaCh, 1% H₂O₂, n=3).

In order to evaluate the applicability of the MIm in neonate clinical samples, the micromotors propulsion was tested in serum and plasma media, while compared with their behavior in PBS buffer. **Figure IV.1.8A** and **Video IV.1.S1** illustrates the efficient propulsion of the anti-CRP rGO/Ni/Pt micromotors in serum and plasma samples under the optimized conditions. As expected, a diminished speed was observed in serum, although it did not affect the function of our micromotors. In plasma, and in order to obtain an adequate propulsion, it was necessary an increment of H₂O₂ concentration until 2% to obtain similar speeds and similar amount of motile micromotors than those found in serum.

Taking into account the higher viscosity and lower surface tension of the blood matrices, due to the presence of great amount of proteins, micromotors propulsion without the presence of surfactant was also tested. If surfactant is not added, micromotors speed was noticeably reduced in both matrices, requiring an

increment in H₂O₂ concentration up to 4% in plasma (**Figure IV.1.8B**). Therefore, surfactant was also added for blood samples analysis.

Figure IV.1.8. Functionalized rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors swimming in buffer (PBS), serum and plasma. (A) With surfactant (NaCh 1.5% and 1% H₂O₂). (B) Without surfactant (3% H₂O₂). Special propulsion conditions for plasma samples are also indicated in the figure: (A) (NaCh 1.5% and 2% H₂O₂). (B) 4% H₂O₂. Scale bar: 5 μm .

To demonstrate that H₂O₂ levels used in this work did not affect the immunoassay performance, the influence of H₂O₂ levels (0–5%) was also evaluated. No differences in the cathodic currents were observed during the immunocomplex formation on board of anti-CRP micromotors (without PtNPs catalytic layer as control, **Figure IV.1.9A**) below H₂O₂ levels of 3%. Furthermore, no negative effect on the immunoassay performance due to the presence of the NaCh at 1.5% was neither observed (**Figure IV.1.9B**). These results confirmed that the overall propulsion conditions (1% of H₂O₂ for PBS and serum and 2% for plasma samples, 1.5% of NaCh) did not influence negatively on the overall MIm performance.

Figure IV.1.9. Effect of the H₂O₂ fuel (A) and NaCh surfactant (B) concentrations on the immunoassay performance (mechanical stirring for 5 min).

Finally, serum certified reference material (CRM) and plasma samples from neonates with suspected sepsis were analysed. The results listed in **Table IV.1.2** revealed an excellent accuracy of our micromotor-based method when SCRM was analysed ($E_r = 1\%$). Interestingly, the results obtained by our MIm in comparison with those declared by the Hospital (BRAHMS CRPus KRYPTOR) for preterm neonate plasma samples, did not show differences. These valuable results revealed further applicability of our approach for clinically relevant sample analysis.

Table IV.1.2. Analysis of serum certified reference material and preterm neonate plasma samples.^a

Samples	CRP _{MIm} (µg/mL)	CRP _{reference} (µg/mL)
CRM Serum	40.8 ± 3.8	41.2 ± 2.5
Neonate Plasma Sample 1	2.4 ± 0.4	< 2.9
Neonate Plasma Sample 2	29 ± 6	34
Neonate Plasma Sample 3	52 ± 3	58.4

^aResults are expressed as Mean Values ± SD (n=3). Color code: green, orange and red for low, medium and high CRP levels, respectively.

Overall, our approach exhibited key advantages such as simplicity, rapidity and reliability of the analysis using extremely low volume of clinical samples and covering the entire range of concentrations involved in the clinical sepsis diagnosis. In addition, the possibility of directly measuring these unique neonatal samples in the clinically relevant range of concentrations without any sample manipulation, including dilutions; the simplicity, inherent miniaturization and the automatization potential, make of this approach a promising tool for POC development.

This new strategy become highly competitive to other magnetic-based immunoassay approaches for CRP determination, which can be considered as an alternative competitor to magnetic micromotors. Indeed, in reported works using magnetic beads-based electrochemical (Meyer *et al.*, 2007; Esteban-Fernández de Ávila *et al.*, 2013; Yang *et al.*, 2015; Gan *et al.*, 2012a,b; Molinero-Fernández *et al.*, 2019) and optical immunosensors (Zhu *et al.*, 2010; Yang *et al.*, 2014; Zhao *et al.*, 2017; Huttunen *et al.*, 2016); the determination of CRP was carried out using more complex nano-architectural approaches (Zhao *et al.*, 2017), with longer analysis times (without exception, some of them even superior than 1 h (Esteban-Fernández de Ávila *et al.*, 2013; Gan *et al.*, 2012a), using larger sample volumes (Esteban-Fernández de Ávila *et al.*, 2013; Zhu *et al.*, 2010; Molinero-Fernández *et al.*, 2019) and with very narrow linear intervals (Yang *et al.*, 2015) making it difficult to measure the biomarker directly at different clinical levels of interest as well.

4. Conclusions

Analytical capabilities of smartly designed and constructed rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors into three layers (rGO for antibody sandwich functionalization, Ni for magnetic guidance and stopped flow operations and PtNPs for catalytic bubble propulsion) for CRP immunosensing *on the fly* has been demonstrated to be very useful for neonatal sepsis diagnosis.

Under controlled propulsion conditions, the new approach using magnetic anti-CRP rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors offered a rapid *on-the-fly* (5 min) and accurate

CRP determination in serum and preterm babies' plasma samples using extremely small volume of samples (<10 μ L).

This new approach becomes a promising tool for on-site/bed side clinical analysis, especially in those fields where limited sample amount is available, like neonatology. Micromotors-based biosensing opens a new path for future screening diagnostics; drawing new hopes in the diagnostics landscape, mainly in those dealing with extremely low sample volumes-based ones.

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Associated content

Supporting Information

Video IV.1.S1. rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors swimming in different biological samples.

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